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A Creative Folio

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The Dreamer's Catch

She was dreamer, steadfast, hopeful and fueled by passion. In her young days, at an age where she was clueless of how the profession works, it was her dream. She had written it boldly in her graduation wish: to become a teacher. And true enough, she nailed it, she graduated with the degree she has been dreaming of for years.

After graduation, she found a teaching job in a private institution. In every lesson she delivered, she was fire, creativity, energy, and a deep desire to inspire change. She then pushed herself further, determined to become one of licensed professional teachers in her country. With the Lord's guidance and perseverance, she passed.

She believed that life would be as flawless as how she planned it, imaginative, with time-frame and full of dreams of a brighter tomorrow.

As time went by, she was encouraged to take a leap and apply to a better institution one that offered greater opportunities and a higher salary. She was determined, convinced that her dreams would fully come true once she entered that institution. She prepared tirelessly and eventually made it to what they called the "ranking".

Questions echoed in her mind: Was this my catch? Am I finally reaching my dreams?"

She waited for a call, a single call that could answer her questions. Days turned into months. Months stretched into years. But the call never came. Hoped slowly faded into sorrow, and the once-burning fire of teaching became unfamiliar in her heart.

Then one ordinary day, while she was strolling inside the mall, a little girl of about four years old stood in front of her and asked

"You are my sisters' teacher, right?"

With a calm smile, she knelt and asked the little girl of what is the name of her sister.

"Her name is Becca", the little girl replied. Then, with eyes full of certainty, she added,

"You are my sister's best teacher. When I grow up, I want to transfer to my Ate's school and I want you to be my teacher too".

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Her heart trembled.

In that moment, she realized something she had almost forgotten. Her dream was never just about entering an institution or receiving a higher salary. Her true dream was to touch hearts, to change lives and to leave marks that time could never erase. Teaching was never about money, it was about passion, purpose, and love poured into every learner.

She was still hopeful to get the call to come. But now, her dreams no longer chased numbers or titles. Instead, she dreamed of catching her learner's futures, of shaping creative, critical thinkers who would rise in this new generation.

And perhaps, she finally understood:

The dream was never lost. It was already living, in the hearts she had taught.